

The Effect of Digital Marketing Implementation Towards Muslim Fashion Brand Awareness and Brand Image on Covid'19 Pandemic

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ABSTRACT: Digital marketing has a positive impact on brand awareness and brand image. This can have a good effect on the economy as it can increase brand awareness and brand image of Muslim fashion brands. This good economic effect will translate into improved company performance in covid'19. This study aims to determine the influence of the company's digital marketing on brand awareness and brand image on covid'19 in Muslim fashion brands. This study uses multiple regression on panel data from a sample of 100 respondents based in Indonesia. The variable of this research is digital marketing in Muslim fashion brands. Other variables are brand awareness and brand image to see what effect digital marketing has on these variables in covid'19. The results of the study resulted in t value > t table and sig < 0.05 from each hypothesis that everything was declared accepted because t value > t table and sig < 0.05. This study shows a significant influence of digital marketing on Muslim fashion brands on brand awareness and brand image during the covid'19 pandemic.

KEYWORDS: Brand awareness, Brand image, Digital Marketing, Muslim fashion brands

INTRODUCTION

The Coronavirus Disease 2019 (Covid-19) pandemic impacts the Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) national economy. The Covid-19 pandemic poses a threat to the income of SMEs because of the difficulty of running their business, especially in marketing and selling products that are carried out offline. With the development of digital technology today, business actors need to add and or change their marketing and sales methods with Go Online

The role of digital marketing is significant in fashion marketing. Fashion is a global business with a complex structure that operates multiple levels to reach everyone, from fashion designers to those who only buy clothes as a daily necessity (Purwar 2019). Digital marketing is also very close to the fashion industry. It promotes the speed and convenience of clothing trading, buying patterns, payment patterns, up-to-date information, after-sales feedback, etc. (Purwar 2019).

Fashion apparel companies should adopt strategies to meet the volatile needs of consumers, enabling managers in the industry to understand today's consumers and profiling, implementing digital marketing tools (Kulmala, Mesiranta, and Tuominen, 2013; Köse, Ş.G., and Enginkaya, 2017).

According to Kotler (2012), companies must manage their product brands well. Prominent brand marketers often cash enormous sums for advertising to create brand awareness and loyalty. The difference between this study and other studies is in the products studied. And the value that can be added to this research is to help Muslim fashion brands improve their performance to be introduced in Indonesia and abroad because many studies use products or brands. Such as luxury or modern brands. No one has researched Muslim fashion brands yet.

This study examines the impact of digital marketing on brand image and brand awareness for Muslim fashion. This study tries to fill in the gaps and variables mentioned before. This research will help Muslim fashion impact digital marketing on its brand image and awareness.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Digital Marketing

According to (Chaffey and Chadwick 2016), "Digital marketing is applying the internet and related digital technologies in conjunction with traditional communications to achieve marketing objectives." That means that Digital Marketing is an application of the internet and is related to digital technology related to traditional communication to achieve marketing goals. That can increase

consumers' knowledge about profiles, behaviors, values, and loyalty levels, then integrate targeted communications and online services according to everyone's needs.

(Johansson 2010) implies how digital marketing has influenced the process of branding a product. It also talks about how companies create brand equity through brand awareness. The levels of brand awareness are recognition, recall, top-of-mind, and word of mouth. The research revealed different aspects of branding and which part has been highly influenced by social media. It explains brand equity, brand strategy and brand awareness. Digital marketing improves communication with different stakeholders. Hence it is an effective way to manage customer relationships. Therefore, businesses can achieve increased customer awareness through various digital marketing activities. By improving their customers' perception in the market, companies can efficiently gain brand awareness and brand image, which will positively impact business.

Digital marketing is a marketing activity that uses digital media using the internet that utilizes media in the form of web, social media, email, database, and mobile/wireless. And digital tv to increases target consumers and to know the profile, behaviors, product value, and loyalty of customers or target consumers to achieve marketing goals (Chaffey and Chadwick, 2016; Purwana ES, 2017). From the explanation above, it can be concluded that digital marketing is marketing products and services using the internet by utilizing the web, social media, email, databases, mobile/wireless, and digital tv to increase marketing and target consumers. The researchers took social media, website, e-commerce, and online advertising as indicators of the digital marketing dimension.

According to Fika, Salsabilla, and Batangriyan (2020), digital marketing positively and significantly affects brand image. On the other hand, Fitrianna and Aurinawati (2020) state the Influence of Digital Marketing on Increasing Brand Awareness and Brand Image.

Digital marketing variables using Instagram and Facebook significantly influenced brand awareness (Yacub and Mustajab, 2020). According to Husniati Sya'idah *et al.* (2019), digital marketing is effective and efficient for the company in reaching consumers and increasing brand awareness of the product proposed by the company.

Social media/ digital marketing activities influence brand image and brand loyalty. Besides, it has been determined that the most apparent effect is on brand awareness (BİLGİN 2018). The results showed that digital marketing communication impacts brand awareness, and brand awareness impacts purchase intention mediated through customer engagement (Abdullah, 2020).

Brand Awareness

Brand awareness is identifying (recognizing or remembering) a brand in a category with sufficient detail to make a purchase. Brand Awareness (Brand awareness) is the ability of consumers to identify a brand in different conditions, which can be done with brand recognition and recall of a particular brand (Kotler 2012). Brand awareness through repeated exposure so that consumers feel familiar with the Brand. According to Saputro, Paramita, and Warso (2016), Brand awareness is an asset that can last a very long time. Brand awareness is an intangible asset, which includes the Brand, perceived quality, name or image, symbols, and slogans of a brand which are the primary sources of competitive advantage in the future (Aaker and Biel 2013). On the other hand, Rangkuti (2009) states that brand Awareness (brand awareness) is the ability of a prospective buyer to recognize or recall that a brand is part of a particular product category. Meanwhile, Ambolau M, Kusumawati A, and Mawardi M (2015) stated, "Brand awareness is an ability of consumers to identify the brand under different conditions, can be done with the brand recognition and recall to a particular brand." From the definitions that have been described, it can be concluded that brand awareness is the ability of consumers to recognize and recall a brand in sufficient detail to make a purchase.

Recognizing the importance of brand awareness in influencing consumer purchase intentions and purchasing decisions, many companies try to reach the top of mind in the minds of consumers. Consumers are filled with marketing messages in various media to build brand awareness every day.

Based on the explanation above, it can be described that the brand recognition scheme is the level of recognizing and recalling a brand with assistance. And brand recall (recall) is the level of recalling a brand without using the aid as a component that plays a role in forming Brand Awareness (brand awareness). For indicators of brand awareness, the researchers took the recognizing, recalling, dominance, and visual branding.

Brand Image

According to Kotler (2012), brand image is a brand's perception as reflected by brand associations in the minds of consumers. On the other hand, Henslowe (2008) states that brand image is the impression obtained according to knowledge and understanding of facts about people, products, and situations. The object in question is an unknown person, organization, group of people, or other. Image is a view or perception. The accumulation of trust given by individuals will experience a process sooner or later to form a broader and abstract public opinion.

Brand image is a total picture from the target consumer's or customer's mind towards the product or Brand (McDaniel, Howard, and Einstein 2009). Meanwhile, according to Rangkuti (2012), brand image is a set of brand associations formed and attached to the minds of consumers. According to Roslina (2010), brand image is a guide that consumers use to evaluate products when consumers do not have sufficient knowledge. Thus, in this statement, there is a tendency for consumers to choose products that are well known through marketing experience using the product or based on information obtained through various sources. On the other hand, (Pars 2011) emphasize that brand image is an impression formed because of numerous factors (e.g., associations associated with a given brand name, the purchasing experience, the reputation of a given company, forms and measures of advertising, promotion, etc.), which means that it is a complex, inhomogeneous, and an abstract category from the perspective of various recipients. In addition, the brand image must be accepted by the broader community of a particular company (external and internal) which positively distinguishes itself from competing brands in the market. Regarding the logistics service market, Jari, Jouni, and Grant studied the impact of service quality on the outsourcing relationship and argued that the service provider's image plays an essential role in gaining customer loyalty.

Brand image can be analyzed through a prism of four key elements: verbal and visual identification, forms of brand promotion, i.e., marketing communication, and the behaviours of people (employees) linked to a given brand. These elements create a consistent method of activities, significantly impacting brand image, i.e., its identification and perception by surroundings

Based on the description above, it can be concluded that brand image is the impression consumers and the public have of a brand as a reflection of the evaluation of the Brand in question. For indicators on the brand image dimension, the researchers took the impression, perception, reputation, and attractiveness.

Hypothesis

H1: There is a significant influence of digital marketing towards brand awareness in a Muslim fashion brand.

H2: There is a significant influence of brand awareness towards the brand image of a Muslim fashion brand.

H3: There is a significant influence of digital marketing towards the brand image of a Muslim fashion brand.

METHODOLOGY

Type of Study

Business research is defined as a systematic, organized, and data-based activity to identify a specific problem and discover solutions. Business research must provide the necessary information to solve the problem (Uma Sekaran & Bougie 2013).

According to Uma Sekaran & Bougie (2013), the type of research is divided into three categories: an exploratory study, a descriptive study, and a causal study. Descriptive analyses are used to provide descriptions of an event or situation based on the data that has been collected. Meanwhile, causal research is used to identify one variable's relationship and impact on others. The causal-explanatory study is the type of education examined by the analysis, or more variables can change.

Population and Sampling

A population is a whole group of people, events, or things that the researcher wants to analyze in the study, which will direct the researcher to a conclusion for the research (Zikmund et al., 2013). The sample is defined as the subgroup or subset of the analyzed population that are the selected population members. The researcher will conclude the sample, reflecting the result from the population (Sekaran & Bougie 2016). The population sample mean is Millennial (age 17- 40), with domicile in Indonesia.

Based on (Kumar Ranjit 2019), there are two sampling methods: probability and non-probability. Probability sampling is a sampling method that follows the probability theory where all the elements in the population have the same independent chances to be selected as a research sample. In contrast, non-probability sampling is defined as a method that does not follow the probability theory, where all population elements do not have equal chances to be selected as a study sample.

This research will use non-probability judgment sampling since there are specific criteria for consumers aware of and purchasing from Muslim fashion brands in Indonesia. The sample is conducted with judgment methods because only guests will take the information. The respondent should be aware of Muslim fashion brands and their products.

Data Source and Collection

This study will use qualitative methods. For qualitative methods, data collection uses surveys. Respondents taken for this survey are Muslim fashion customers.

There are two types of data: primary and secondary (Douglas et al., 2015). Primary data is defined as original and factual data collected by the researcher for the first time to find a solution to the problem at hand. In addition, there are four main sources of primary data: surveys, interviews, experiments, and observation. On the other hand, Secondary data is the analysis and explanation of primary data already collected or produced for other purposes by other researchers, such as annual reports. It aids in increasing the credibility of research findings. This research is going to use primary data. The primary data is the questionnaires answered by consumers of a Muslim fashion brand who were aware of and purchased Muslim fashion brands within the last year and intended to acquire them in the future.

In contrast, secondary data are the previous studies that support the primary data. Data will be collected by doing an online questionnaire (Google form) because of the COVID-19 pandemic. The questionnaire will separate into the valid respondents: individuals who have had at least one product in the past year with Muslim fashion brands. In this research, the Likert scale method will be a sample method. The Likert scale indicates agreement or disagreement with numerous statements about an object, person, and attitude. In addition, the Likert scale contains five or seven points (Taherdoost 2016). The Likert scale allows individuals to show how much they agree or disagree with a specific statement.

ANALYSIS

Descriptive Statistic Analysis

The descriptive information includes the number of samples (N), the minimum and maximum values, and the mean and standard deviation calculation.

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
TOTAL_DM	100	13	40	33,38	4,447
TOTAL_BA	100	10	40	26,34	6,431
TOTAL_BI	100	11	40	29,53	5,389
Valid N (listwise)	100				

in the questionnaire, a 5-point Likert scale was used, in which the smallest value (1) indicates that the respondents strongly disagree with the statement. In contrast, the most significant weight (5) suggests that the respondents strongly agree. The mean score for each variable is above 30 and 1 below 30, ranging from 22.93 to 33.38, indicating that the respondents' perception toward each variable is generally favourable. Moreover, the standard deviation for each variable is below 30, ranging from 3.462 to 6.431, indicating that the values in each dataset are usually close to the mean value.

Reliability Test

The reliability test was conducted by looking at the internal consistency with the Cronbach Alpha method. The reliability values of all the variables of this study. All variables in this study have a value > 0.6. Therefore, it can be said that all measuring instruments used to measure these three variables are reliable.

Reliability Test

Variable	Cronbach Alpha
Digital Marketing	0.813
Brand Awareness	0.895
Brand Image	0.887

Validity Test

Item	n = 100;0.05	Pearson
DM1	0.195	0.604
DM2	0.195	0.638
DM3	0.195	0.732
DM4	0.195	0.684
DM5	0.195	0.737
DM6	0.195	0.733
DM7	0.195	0.620
DM8	0.195	0.623

This study tests the validity of digital marketing tools by comparing the r count with the r table with the digital marketing correlation test. The results of testing the validity of this measuring instrument. All items in the digital marketing variable significantly correlate with the total score of the D.M. variable. After that, the researcher visited the value of the r table with a sample of 100. Therefore, the value of the r table = 0.195. By comparing the calculated r-value in the range of 0.604-0.737 > from the r-table value of 0.195, it can be concluded that all items in the Digital marketing variable are valid.

Item	n = 100;0.05	Pearson
BA1	0.195	0.625
BA2	0.195	0.819
BA3	0.195	0.827
BA4	0.195	0.856
BA5	0.195	0.853
BA6	0.195	0.844
BA7	0.195	0.802
BA8	0.195	0.455

This study tests the validity of brand awareness measuring tools by comparing the r count with the r table and brand awareness correlation test. The results of testing the validity of this measuring instrument. All items in the brand awareness variable significantly correlate with the B.A. variable's total score. After that, the researcher visited the value of the r table with a sample of 100. Therefore, the value of the r table = 0.195. By comparing the calculated r-value in the range of 0.455-0.856 > from the r-table value of 0.195, it can be concluded that all items in the Brand awareness variable are valid.

Item	n = 100;0.05	Pearson
BI1	0.195	0.728
BI2	0.195	0.815
BI3	0.195	0.843
BI4	0.195	0.744
BI5	0.195	0.762
BI6	0.195	0.482
BI7	0.195	0.838
BI8	0.195	0.807

This study tests the validity of brand image measuring tools by comparing the r count with the r table with the brand image correlation test. The results of testing the validity of this measuring instrument. All items in the brand image variable have a significant correlation with the total score of the B.I. Variable. After that, the researcher visited the value of the r table with a sample

of 100. Therefore, the value of the r table = 0.195. By comparing the calculated r -value in the range of 0.482-0.843 > from the r -table value of 0.195, it can be concluded that all items in the Brand image variable are valid.

Hypothesis Test

H1: There is a significant influence between digital marketing and brand awareness on a Muslim fashion brand.

It is known from the figure above that the value sig. for the influence of digital marketing on brand awareness is $0.000 < 0.05$, and the t value is $7.014 > t$ table 1,984, so it can be concluded that H1 is accepted, which means that there is an influence of digital marketing on brand awareness. The results of hypothesis testing regarding the relationship of digital marketing to brand awareness show a significant effect of digital marketing on brand awareness. These results apply to all digital marketing groups: social media, websites, online advertising, and e-commerce. The use of digital marketing influences brand awareness. The descriptive statistics show that digital marketing responds relatively positively to items related to brand awareness. Still, a high score implies that digital marketing, in general, has a significant impact on brand awareness. That means the use of digital marketing on Muslim fashion brands can increase brand awareness, gain product awareness, and know better about the product of Muslim fashion brands because the results of the hypothesis are accepted.

H2: There is a significant influence between brand awareness and image on Muslim fashion brands.

It is known from the figure above that the value sig. for the influence of brand awareness on brand image is $0.000 < 0.05$, and the t value is $11,624 > t$ table 1,984, so it can be concluded that H2 is accepted, which means that there is an influence of brand awareness on brand image. The results of hypothesis testing regarding the relationship of brand awareness to brand image show a significant effect of brand awareness on brand image. These results apply to all brand awareness groups, name-brand recognition, brand recall, brand dominance, and visual branding. The use of brand awareness influences the Brand's image. The descriptive statistics show that brand awareness positively responds to items related to brand image. Still, a high score implies that brand awareness, in general, has a significant impact on brand image. That means the increase in brand awareness of Muslim fashion brands can increase the brand image and get to know Muslim fashion brands better because the results of the hypothesis are accepted.

H3: A Muslim fashion brand significantly influences digital marketing and brand image.

It is known from the figure above that the value sig. for the influence of digital marketing on brand image is $0.000 < 0.05$, and the t value is $8,205 > t$ table 1,984, so it can be concluded that H3 is accepted, which means that there is an influence of digital marketing on brand image. The results of hypothesis testing regarding the relationship of digital marketing to brand image show a significant effect of digital marketing on brand image. These results apply to all digital marketing groups: social media, websites, online advertising, and e-commerce. The use of digital marketing influences brand image. The descriptive statistics show that digital marketing responds relatively positively to items related to brand image. Still, a high score implies that digital marketing, in general, has a significant impact on brand image. That means using digital marketing on Muslim fashion brands can increase brand image, gain a good image, and know better about the image of Muslim fashion brands because the results of the hypothesis are accepted.

CONCLUSION

Based on the respondent's profile, the results show that 100% of the consumer of Muslim fashion is in the men and women gender, as it is always believed that the primary target market is men/females with a range of 17-40 years old. However, during the pandemic of Covid-19, consumers that have the occupation of students and the private sector got less impacted by the covid-19 situation. It can be assumed that through the Covid-19 situation, many people can earn high incomes through social media platforms (Tiktok and Instagram) by working with several well-known brands. The respondent uses those additional incomes to purchase a product from a Muslim fashion brand through digital marketing, brand awareness, and brand image on Covid-19.

Data Analysis results measuring all the variables begin with the descriptive analysis to see the mean value of digital marketing, brand awareness, and brand image during covid'19. The result shows a positive response to that variable Secondly, begin with the validity and reliability tests to see the validity and reliability of all variables during covid'19. The result shows that all variables are valid because the point is above the r table. And the result for the reliability of all variables is correct because of the Cronbach alpha above 0.6.

The regression analysis results answer the research question and hypothesis design in chapter 1.

- a. Digital marketing has an impact on brand awareness. The result shows that there is a regression correlation between the variables. While hypothesis 1 is accepted. Therefore, it can assume that digital marketing significantly affects brand awareness in Muslim fashion brands. That means digital marketing is vital in increasing the brand awareness of Muslim fashion brands.
- b. Brand awareness has an impact on brand image. The result shows that there is a regression correlation between the variables. While hypothesis 2 is accepted. Therefore, it can assume that brand awareness significantly affects the brand image of Muslim fashion brands. That means increasing brand awareness can improve their brand image of Muslim fashion brands.
- c. Digital marketing has an impact on the brand image. The result shows that there is a regression correlation between the variables. While hypothesis 3 is accepted. Therefore, it can assume that digital marketing has a significant effect on the brand image of Muslim fashion brands. That means digital marketing can also increase the Muslim fashion brand's brand image.

This research shows that interest is the critical dimension of the digital marketing strategy of brand awareness and brand image. Furthermore, Muslim fashion brands use digital marketing to increase their brand awareness and image of covid'19. Therefore, digital marketing must be unique to increase brand awareness, brand image, and income to succeed in selling.

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